

**Traumatic shock - causes, symptoms, classification, diagnosis, first aid,
treatment and prevention.**

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Annotation: In this article, a life-threatening condition; as a result of excessively strong effects, it is expressed by a violation of the functioning of the nervous, endocrine, blood circulation, respiratory systems, and metabolism. It is often explained that it occurs due to injury, burns, surgery, blood transfusion, myocardial infarction, heart failure, etc.

Key words: cause, symptoms, diagnosis, aid, treatment, prevention, blood, life, patient, surgery, infarction, trauma, shock, hospital.

Traumatic shock is a pathological condition that occurs as a result of blood loss and pain in trauma and poses a serious threat to the patient's life. Regardless of the reasons for its development, it always manifests itself with the same symptoms. Pathology is diagnosed based on clinical signs. It is necessary to immediately stop the bleeding, restore consciousness and immediately take the patient to the hospital. Treatment of traumatic shock is carried out in the intensive care unit and includes a set of measures to compensate for the resulting disorders. The prognosis

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depends on the severity and stage of the shock, as well as the severity of the injury that caused it.

Traumatic shock is a serious condition, which is the body's reaction to an acute injury, accompanied by severe blood loss and severe pain. It usually develops immediately after the injury and is a direct reaction to the injury, but in certain conditions (additional trauma) it can appear after some time (4-36 hours). can be. This is a life-threatening condition that requires urgent treatment in the intensive care unit. Traumatic shock develops in all types of severe injuries, regardless of their causes, location and damage mechanism. It can occur as a result of knife and gunshot wounds, falls from a height, car accidents, man-made and natural disasters, industrial accidents, etc. Depending on the causes of development, there are several classifications of traumatic shock. Thus, in many Russian manuals on traumatology and orthopedics, shock due to surgical shock, endotoxin shock, crush, burn, air shock and tourniquet shock is distinguished. V.K. Kulagin's classification is widely used. According to it, there are the following types of traumatic shock: Wounded traumatic shock (as a result of mechanical damage). Depending on the location of the injury, it is divided into visceral, lung, brain, limb injuries, multiple injuries, and compression of soft tissues.

1. Operative traumatic shock.
2. Hemorrhagic traumatic shock (develops with internal and external bleeding).
3. Mixed traumatic shock.

Regardless of the causes of traumatic shock, it continues in two stages: erectile (the body tries to compensate for the disturbances) and torpid (compensatory abilities

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are exhausted). Taking into account the severity of the patient's condition in the torpid phase, 4 degrees of shock are distinguished:

I (light). The patient's color is pale, sometimes he looks a little lethargic. Consciousness is clear. Reflexes are reduced. Shortness of breath, heart rate up to 100 beats per minute.

II (average). The patient is sleepy and lethargic. Approximate pulse 140 beats / min.

III (severe). Consciousness remains, the ability to perceive the surrounding world disappears. The skin is earthy gray, the lips, nose and fingertips are cyanotic. Sticky sweat. The pulse is about 160 beats / min.

IV (predagonny and agony). There is no consciousness, the pulse cannot be detected. Signs of traumatic shock

During the erectile phase, the patient is excited, complains of pain, may scream or moan. He looks worried and scared. Often there is aggression, resistance to examination and treatment. The skin is pale, the blood pressure is slightly increased. Tachycardia, tachypnea (acceleration of breathing), trembling of limbs or small twitching of individual muscles are observed. Eyes shine, pupils dilate, vision becomes disturbed. The skin is covered with cold clay-colored sweat. The pulse is rhythmic, the body temperature is normal or slightly elevated. At this stage, the body is still able to compensate for the damage that has occurred. There are no gross violations in the functioning of internal organs, DVS. With the onset of the torpid phase of traumatic shock, the patient becomes indifferent, lethargic, sleepy, depressed. Although the pain does not decrease during this period, the patient stops or almost stops giving signals. He no longer screams and complains, he can lie quietly, moan quietly, or even pass out. Even with manipulations in the area of

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damage, no reaction is observed. Blood pressure gradually decreases and heart rate increases. The pulse in the peripheral arteries weakens, becomes thready, and then ceases to be detected. The patient's eyes are blurred, sunken, the pupils are dilated, the gaze is motionless, there are shadows under the eyes. Clear pallor of the skin, cyanosis of the mucous membranes, lips, nose and fingertips is observed. The skin is dry and cold, the elasticity of tissues decreases. Facial features are sharpened, nasolabial folds are smoothed. Body temperature is normal or low (temperature may also increase due to wound infection). The patient feels cold even in a warm room. Often there are convulsions, forced excretion of feces and urine. Signs of intoxication are identified. The patient suffers from thirst, the tongue is covered with mucus, the lips are dry and cracked. Nausea and in severe cases even vomiting is possible. Due to the progressive deterioration of kidney function, the amount of urine decreases even with heavy drinking. Urine is dark, concentrated, painful, anuria (absence of urine) may be observed.

Traumatic shock is diagnosed when relevant symptoms, presence of new injuries, or other possible cause of this pathology are identified. To assess the condition of the victim, periodic measurements of pulse and blood pressure are carried out and laboratory tests are ordered. The list of diagnostic procedures is determined by the pathological condition that caused the development of traumatic shock.

At the initial stage in the hospital, resuscitators-anesthesiologists pour saline (lactazol, Ringer's solution) and colloid (reopolyglucin, polyglucin, gelatinol, etc.) solutions. After determining the Rh and blood group, transfusion of these solutions is continued together with blood and plasma. Adequate breathing is ensured by airway, oxygen therapy, tracheal intubation, or mechanical ventilation. Anesthesia

is continued. Catheterization of the urinary bladder is performed to accurately determine the amount of urine. Surgical interventions are carried out according to vital guidelines in the amount necessary to save life and prevent further exacerbation of shock. They stop bleeding and heal wounds, block and immobilize fractures, eliminate pneumothorax, etc. Hormone therapy and dehydration are prescribed, drugs are used to combat brain hypoxia, and metabolic disorders are corrected.

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